

SACQSP2025-80

Introducing SCABE Theory: A Theoretical Framework for Quantity Surveyors and the Sustainability – Climate Nexus

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Abstract

The accelerating climate crisis compels a fundamental reappraisal of the Quantity Surveyor's (QS) role within South Africa's built environment. Traditionally confined to cost estimation, procurement, and contractual control, the QS profession is increasingly confronted with the imperative to embed sustainability and resilience at the core of its practice. This paper undertakes a narrative literature review, drawing on recent scholarship from Scopus, Web of Science and IBSS from the authors selective reading pool, to synthesise knowledge at the intersection of sustainability, climate action, and professional transformation. Five thematic strands emerge: the centrality of sustainability and climate imperatives, the inadequacy of the traditional QS role, persistent barriers to change, enabling drivers and opportunities, and the new competencies required for future practice.

The study advances the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory, constructed through Dubin's (1978) interpretive post positivist model of theory building. SCABE specifies constructs, propositions, boundaries, and system states that capture the QS profession's evolution from 'cost-centric equilibrium', through 'transitional disequilibrium', toward a 'sustainability-centric equilibrium'. It demonstrates how competency barriers, skills deficits, cost perceptions, regulatory weakness, moderate professional adaptation, while future drivers, digitalisation, green finance, energy costs, and policy momentum, enable transformation. The theory positions the QS as a strategic actor capable of operationalising sustainability and climate imperatives through life cycle costing, circular economy strategies, and climate-risk advisory.

Epistemologically, SCABE complements recent frameworks such as social tipping processes, green and circular building theory, resilience modelling, and social innovation in the built environment, by supplying a profession-specific lens that bridges macro-level imperatives with micro-level practice. Normatively, it charts a pathway for education, practice, policy, and professional leadership to reposition Qs as agents of systemic change. The study concludes that unless the QS profession embraces this transformation, it risks marginalisation; conversely, by adopting SCABE, Qs can reassert their relevance as architects of a just, resilient, and sustainable built environment.

Keywords: Climate Action, Circular Economy, Green Building, Quantity Surveyor, SCABE Theory.

Introduction

In April 2022, the city of Durban in South Africa was devastated by catastrophic floods that claimed over 540 lives, displaced thousands, and inflicted billions of rand in damage to infrastructure and housing (Engelbrecht et al., 2025; Nhamo, Chapungu & Mutanda, 2025). Such disasters are not isolated incidents but rather the manifestation of an escalating climate crisis in which droughts, water

scarcity, and extreme weather events increasingly define South Africa's socio-economic trajectory (Vogel & Swilling, 2018; Hellberg, 2020). The built environment occupies a critical position within this challenge: it contributes nearly 40% of global energy consumption and emissions Shin et al. (2023), while South Africa's construction industry alone accounts for almost one-fifth of the national carbon footprint (Labaran, Mathur & Farouq, 2021). Confronting this reality requires not only technological innovation but also the redefinition of professional roles within the sector.

Traditionally, Quantity Surveyors (Qs) have served as financial custodians, focusing on cost estimation, procurement, contract administration, and budgetary control (Cruywagen & Liale, 2017). Yet in a context where the production of cement alone releases approximately one kilogram of carbon dioxide per kilogram produced Akintayo, Olanrewaju & Olanrewaju (2024), financial oversight without environmental foresight is increasingly untenable. A growing body of scholarship has recognised that the profession's traditional scope is misaligned with contemporary imperatives of sustainability, resilience, and social equity (Noor, Tobi & Fathi, 2024; Prabhu Desai & D'souza, 2024). In work focused on the local complexities of sustainable development financing in South Africa, extending this debate by examining barriers to sustainable development in South Africa from an end-user perspective Weaich et al. (2023) and the intersections of green technology investment and its effects on youth unemployment (Weaich, Weaich et al., 2024). These studies underscore, the realities of sustainability, being it environmental, social or economic, the need to reconceptualise the QS as a strategic actor, capable of embedding sustainability principles at the inception of projects, and the greater development sphere, rather than responding reactively once design and cost frameworks are already entrenched, but poorly defined, fragmented across different domains of knowledge.

Nevertheless, despite this problem, extensive research into green buildings, life cycle assessments (LCA), and digitalisation through Building Information Modelling (BIM), gaps remain. Much of the literature privileges environmental science perspectives while overlooking the institutional, financial, and professional dynamics that condition the feasibility of sustainable construction in the Global South (Cooper, Ramabodu & Mashwama, 2022; Bothma, 2025). On the other hand, the agency of the QS, situated at the critical nexus of cost, value, and decision-making, has been underexplored in both academic and policy discourse. This omission has consequences: without embedding QS expertise into sustainability frameworks, barriers such as the "knowing-doing gap" (Pfeffer and Sutton, 2008), in theory, the perception of prohibitive upfront costs, and persistent skills deficits will continue to obstruct meaningful transformation.

Therefore, the aim of this paper is to critically examine and reposition the role of the QS in advancing sustainability and climate action in South Africa's built environment, framed within the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory. In synthesising the literature, the study identifies how Qs can evolve from cost-centric managers to strategic advisors who embed resilience, circularity, and long-term value into construction projects.

From this aim, the central research question is posed:

How can Quantity Surveyors, within the South African built environment, transition from a traditional cost-management role to strategic enablers of sustainability and climate action, thereby operationalising the SCABE Theory?

To address this question, the paper first conceptualises sustainability and climate action within the built environment, situating them within South Africa's socio-economic realities and global frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (Adewunmi, Simbanegavi & Weaich, 2024). It then interrogates the evolving mandate of the QS, outlining the competencies required for sustainability leadership and the barriers to their realisation (Weaich, Ndlovu, et al., 2024). Finally, it synthesises these insights into a forward-looking discussion of SCABE Theory, drawing implications for practice, policy, education, and professional leadership (Alade & Windapo, 2021).

Narrative Literature Review

This paper employs a narrative literature review to synthesise existing scholarship on the intersection of sustainability, climate action, and the evolving role of Quantity Surveyors (Qs) within the South African built environment, dividing its snowballed collection of literature into themes (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2023). The purpose is not only to collate existing knowledge but to critically interrogate how different bodies of literature converge, where they diverge, and where gaps

persist (Machi & McEvoy, 2022). Through this method, five thematic strands emerge, each offering insights into both the challenges and opportunities shaping the QS profession's future trajectory (Guest, MacQueen & Namey, 2011).

Theme 1: Sustainability and Climate Imperatives in the Built Environment

Sustainability in the built environment is widely understood as the integration of environmental, economic, and social goals (Masotya et al., 2024; Simbanegavi, Mutsindikwa et al., 2024; Weaich, 2024). Globally, the built environment contributes approximately 40% of energy consumption and emissions Shin et al. (2023), and in South Africa, construction accounts for nearly 20% of national GHG emissions (Labaran, Mathur & Farouq, 2021). Green Building (GB), also known as Sustainable Building (SB), has thus been promoted as a central strategy (Maseko, 2022; Patil et al., 2024; Simbanegavi, Weaich et al., 2024). Yet, despite policy efforts and legislative strides Bothma, (2025), the translation of these ideals into widespread practice remains limited. Scholars refer to this as the “knowing–doing gap” (Pfeffer & Sutton, 2008).

Theme 2: The Evolving Mandate of the Quantity Surveyor

The QS profession has historically prioritised cost estimation, procurement, and contract administration (Cruywagen & Llale, 2017). Increasingly, however, these traditional roles appear insufficient to address climate imperatives (Ilmi et al., 2021). Emerging scholarship calls for the QS to become a strategic advisor, embedding sustainability, circularity, and resilience into project lifecycles (Noor, Tobi & Fathi, 2024; Prabhu Desai & D'souza, 2024). The integration of digital technologies, particularly BIM, has further expanded the QS's potential influence in early-stage decision-making (Akinshipe et al., 2021). The QS's critical position in mediating between cost, value, and sustainable outcomes, yet this role remains underexplored in mainstream policy and academic discourse (Yogeshwaran, Perera & Ariyachandra, 2018; Terblanche & Root, 2024; Wong, Lim & Azizi, 2024).

Theme 3: Barriers to Transformation

Persistent barriers impede QS-led sustainability. These include perceptions of prohibitive upfront costs De Wet-Billings (2023), inadequate industry knowledge and training Wu et al., (2024), and inconsistently enforced regulations (Cooper, Ramabodu & Mashwama, 2022). Social inclusivity also remains an issue, as demographic imbalances within the QS profession risk reproducing inequities (McKeever, 2024). Without overcoming these barriers, sustainability will remain peripheral to mainstream practice.

Theme 4: Drivers and Opportunities

Despite these challenges, opportunities are expanding. Rising energy costs improve the relative competitiveness of green alternatives (Bothma, 2025). Green finance mechanisms, such as sustainability-linked loans, are gaining traction (Adewunmi, Simbanegavi & Weaich, 2024; Weaich, Weaich et al., 2024). Digitalisation, particularly BIM, enables cost-linked sustainability modelling (Alade & Windapo, 2021; Ismail et al., 2023; Ao et al., 2024). The QS's early-stage influence in project conception uniquely positions the profession to align projects with sustainability targets from inception.

Theme 5: Competencies for the Future QS

To remain relevant, Qs may need to acquire sustainability-focused competencies: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Whole Life Costing (WLC), Circular Economy (CE) literacy, and sustainability-oriented risk management (Oke et al., 2025). Beyond technical skills, soft skills such as leadership, communication, and ethical judgement are equally critical (Wong, Lim & Azizi, 2024). Without this transformation, the profession risks marginalisation.

Contextualising the Themes

The literature review reveals five interrelated themes that together illuminate both the challenges and opportunities confronting the QS profession in the age of sustainability and climate imperatives. The first concerns the overarching pressures of sustainability itself. The built environment is now widely understood as a sphere in which environmental, economic, and social goals must be integrated if development is to be viable (Masotya et al., 2024; Simbanegavi, Mutsindikwa et al., 2024; Weaich,

2024). Yet despite the clear evidence that the sector contributes almost 40% of global emissions Shin et al. (2023), and nearly 20% in South Africa alone Labaran, Mathur and Farouq, (2021), the translation of policy ambitions into practice remains uneven. Green Building (GB), or Sustainable Building (SB), has been promoted as a cornerstone strategy (Maseko, 2022); Patil et al., 2024); Simbanegavi, Weaich, et al., 2024), yet its adoption has been hampered by what scholars term the “knowing–doing gap” Pfeffer and Sutton (2008), wherein policy and technical clarity fail to achieve systemic uptake.

The second theme addresses the evolving mandate of the QS. Historically defined by cost estimation, procurement, and contract administration Cruywagen and Llaie (2017), the traditional role is increasingly inadequate when measured against climate imperatives. Contemporary scholarship argues that QSs must expand their remit to act as strategic advisors, embedding principles of sustainability, circularity, and resilience into the project lifecycle (Noor, Tobi & Fathi, 2024; Prabhu Desai & D'souza, 2024). Digitalisation, particularly through Building Information Modelling (BIM), enhances the potential of QSs to shape project outcomes at conception (Akinshipe et al., 2021). This mediating function, positioning the QS as a bridge between cost, value, and sustainability, though this role remains underexplored in mainstream discourse (Yogeshwaran, Perera & Ariyachandra, 2018; Terblanche & Root, 2024; Wong, Lim & Azizi, 2024). The third theme considers the barriers that obstruct this transformation. Chief among these are persistent perceptions of prohibitive upfront costs De Wet-Billings (2023), deficits in professional knowledge and training Wu et al. (2024), and inconsistently enforced regulatory frameworks (Cooper, Ramabodu & Mashwama, 2022). In light of this, demographic imbalances within the profession raise concerns of inclusivity, with the risk that inequality within the QS body may reproduce inequities in the built environment itself (McKeever, 2024). Unless such barriers are overcome, sustainability is likely to remain peripheral. In counterpoint, the fourth theme points to emerging drivers and opportunities. Rising energy costs have begun to tip the balance in favour of sustainable alternatives Bothma (2025), while the growth of green finance instruments, such as sustainability-linked loans, provides new levers for feasibility (Adewunmi, Simbanegavi & Weaich, 2024). Digitalisation through BIM allows for cost-linked sustainability modelling, enhancing both transparency and integration (Adebowale & Agumba, 2023; Cartlidge, 2023; Ismail et al., 2023). Given their early-stage influence on development projects, QSs are uniquely positioned to ensure that projects are aligned with sustainability objectives from inception (Prabhu Desai & D'souza, 2024).

The fifth and final theme highlights the competencies required to sustain this evolution. Beyond their traditional technical skills, QSs must now acquire proficiency in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) Centobelli et al. (2023), Whole Life Costing (WLC) Georgiadou, (2019), and Circular Economy (CE) literacy Schmitz, (2024), coupled with sustainability-oriented risk management (Oke et al., 2025). Yet technical proficiency alone will not suffice: the profession must also cultivate soft skills, leadership, communication, and ethical judgement, if it is to occupy a credible and influential position within the sustainability transition (Wong, Lim & Azizi, 2024). Without such transformation, the QS profession risks marginalisation at precisely the moment when its expertise could prove most indispensable.

Research Methodology and Method

The methodological architecture of this study is best understood through the heuristic adaptation of the research onion Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2023), which allows one to peel back each layer of research design in turn, situating choices within broader philosophical and procedural commitments. At its outermost layer, the study adopts a research philosophy that is interpretivist in orientation, albeit tempered by a postpositivist concern for rigour and structure (Phillips & Burbules, 2000). This dual stance acknowledges that sustainability and climate action are inherently social phenomena, mediated by perceptions, values, and institutions, yet also recognises the need for systematic and replicable frameworks, here provided through Dubin (1969) interpretive post positivistic theory-building model.

Peeling back a further layer, the study employs a research approach that is abductive rather than strictly deductive or inductive, building arguments from secondary data (Mitchell & Education, 2018). Deduction, with its hypothesis-testing closure, and induction, with its grounded generalisations, both fall short of capturing the complexity of sustainability transitions (Booth et al., 2016; Field, 2024). Abduction, by contrast, allows the researcher to move iteratively between theory and observation, drawing plausible inferences and refining constructs as new insights emerge (Peirce, 1865). It is precisely this abductive reasoning that enables the articulation of the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory as both descriptive and normative (Dubin, 1969).

The methodological choice taken is qualitative, privileging depth of insight and interpretive richness over breadth of numerical generalisation (Booth et al., 2016; Field, 2024). This is not to deny the value of quantitative analysis, but to recognise that the transformation of professional identity, here, the evolution of the QS from cost manager to sustainability strategist is a process better understood through conceptual synthesis and interpretive theorisation than through statistical measurement alone.

At the level of research strategy, the study adopts a narrative literature review (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2023). Unlike systematic reviews which emphasise comprehensiveness, the narrative approach is more selective, allowing for the critical interrogation of sources and the weaving together of diverse strands of literature in a snowballed approach to data collection, into a coherent thematic account, rather than a broad account. Databases such as Scopus, Web of Science and IBSS were utilised to ensure scholarly reliability, with no particular course of action or prompting other than using the keywords, sustainability and quantity surveyor, the approach to literature searching was extended by referring to recent literature cited in the papers themselves, with subjective opinion on 'what would' and 'would not be' relevant to answering the research question, and thematic saturation was pursued until recurring patterns and gaps became evident (Jesson, Matheson & Lacey, 2012).

The time horizon of the research is cross-sectional, capturing a snapshot of the present state of knowledge and professional practice. However, the abductive orientation lends the study a longitudinal sensitivity, since the SCABE framework anticipates how the role of the QS may evolve across the coming decades in response to climate imperatives and sustainability frameworks such as the SDGs and Paris Agreement (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2023; Weaich, Weaich et al., 2024).

Finally, at the innermost layer of the onion, the study is grounded in techniques and procedures of data collection and analysis. Peer-reviewed articles, conference papers, and relevant policy documents formed the secondary data corpus, if referenced in the articles. These were subjected to thematic analysis, with coding structured around constructs identified in Dubin (1969) model (constructs, propositions, boundaries, and system states). This method allowed for the rigorous synthesis of disparate literatures into a coherent theoretical contribution, ensuring both epistemological clarity and practical relevance (Dubin, 1969; Eisend & Kuß, 2019; Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2023).

In sum, the methodological journey from philosophy to procedures reveals a carefully layered design. Interpretivism, abductive and postpositivistic reasoning, qualitative method, narrative strategy, cross-sectional horizon, and thematic procedures collectively converge to support the development of SCABE Theory. In so doing, the methodology mirrors the very subject of the study: a multi-layered, systemic approach to complex and evolving phenomena in the built environment.

The next section of the study, places Dubin (1969) approach to theory building at the centre of the data analysis, placing propositions and arguments within its analysis, rather than the study's introduction, as the purpose of which is to theorise how the question can be answered and reconceptualised from the data.

Results and Theory Building

Critical Synthesis of Themes

The five themes collectively demonstrate that while the conceptual foundations of sustainability and climate action in the built environment are robust, the profession of Quantity Surveying (QS) remains at a crossroads. On one hand, sustainability has been articulated with great clarity at both global and national levels, with frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and South Africa's energy-efficiency legislation providing a guiding scaffold. On the other hand, the translation of these frameworks into practice is constrained by entrenched perceptions of cost, uneven knowledge distribution, and limited institutional enforcement.

The QS's evolving mandate emerges as both a response to, and an opportunity within, this contested terrain. The profession is uniquely placed to mediate between competing priorities, cost, value, sustainability, and resilience, yet its potential remains under-realised. Where Qs have embraced tools such as Building Information Modelling (BIM) or Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), they demonstrate the capacity to reframe project viability in terms of long-term environmental and social value. However, where Qs remain confined to a traditional cost-centric paradigm, they risk marginalisation by other built environment professionals more adept at articulating sustainability imperatives.

The “knowing–doing gap” is the fulcrum of this challenge: the disjuncture between policy frameworks and practical uptake reveals not only systemic inertia but also the absence of a collective QS voice in sustainability discourse. This silence has consequences. By failing to assert leadership in sustainability, Qs risk ceding their influence at precisely the moment when their expertise is most needed to align projects with climate goals. The stakes are high: leaving this condition unresolved threatens to perpetuate unsustainable construction practices, exacerbate climate vulnerability, and weaken the resilience of South Africa’s built environment.

It is precisely within this tension that the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory is situated. By consolidating insights across themes, SCABE frames the QS as a strategic enabler of systemic change, capable of operationalising sustainability and climate action through financial, technical, and advisory expertise.

Table 1 Five themes

Theme	Key Insights	Barriers Identified	Opportunities / Enablers	QS Implications
1. Sustainability and Climate Imperatives	Built environment central to emissions; GB pivotal for mitigation and adaptation	Knowing–doing gap; weak enforcement	Global frameworks (SDGs); SA policy strides	QS must embed sustainability at project inception
2. Evolving Mandate of QS	Shift from cost-centric to strategic advisor	Profession slow to adapt; risk of marginalisation	BIM, LCA, WLC expand role	QS as sustainability-oriented value advisor
3. Barrier	Perceived high upfront costs, skills gaps, limited inclusivity	Industry inertia; weak policy	—	Without intervention, QS relevance diminishes
4. Drivers	Rising energy costs, green finance, digitalisation	—	Cost competitiveness of green alternatives; policy momentum	QS can leverage market dynamics to drive change
5. Competencies for Future QS	Technical: BIM, LCA, WLC, CE	Lack of training in sustainability	Professional education reform; CPD opportunities	Future-proof QS role depends on skill acquisition

Development of a Framework: Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory

The Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory provides a structured attempt to reconceptualise the role of the Quantity Surveyor (QS) in response to sustainability and climate imperatives. In framing this theory, Dubin (1969) model of theory building is employed. Dubin, (1969) proposed that theory is best understood as a system of constructs and relationships which collectively explain, rather than to traditionally explore, hence the post positivistic stance in the approach: “what is,” “how it works,” and “under what conditions it operates.” In this approach to theory development, SCABE Theory draws together constructs from sustainability science, climate action, and professional transformation to outline both a descriptive and normative framework for the future QS role.

Theoretical Constructs

According to Dubin (1969), the first step in theory building involves defining the core constructs that form the theory’s architecture. SCABE Theory identifies the following:

- Traditional QS Role – characterised by cost estimation, procurement, contract administration, and financial control.
- Current Competencies – technical and professional skills historically emphasised in QS practice.
- Competency Barriers – deficits in sustainability knowledge, training, and inclusivity that moderate transformation
- Traditional Drivers – institutional norms, procurement models, and cost-centric metrics anchoring QS practice.
- Future Drivers – enablers such as BIM, green finance, and regulatory incentives.

- Sustainability Imperatives – the demand to align construction with environmental, social, and economic goals.
- Climate Imperatives – the dual pressures of mitigation and adaptation shaping built environment futures.
- QS Strategic Role – the transitional identity in which QSs expand their advisory scope to encompass lifecycle value, circularity, and resilience.
- SCABE Framework – the consolidation of constructs into a guiding model that integrates sustainability and climate action into QS professional identity.
- Future QS Role – the aspirational role: a sustainability-oriented strategist capable of embedding climate-responsive value systems into construction.
- Forming of Theoretical Propositions

Dubin (1969) states that the lifeblood of theory, in a postpositive context lies in its propositions, for it is through these that constructs are brought into meaningful relationship. Within the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory, five such propositions are advanced. First, the traditional role of the QS, sustained by established competencies and entrenched drivers, remains constrained when confronted with the demands of climate imperatives. Second, the movement toward a more strategic professional identity is shaped by opposing forces: negatively by competency barriers such as skills deficits and institutional inertia, and positively by future drivers including digital technologies, green finance, and regulatory momentum. Third, the mounting pressures of sustainability and climate imperatives create a directional force that renders the strategic role of the QS not optional but increasingly indispensable. Fourth, the SCABE framework itself provides the mechanism Bhaskar, (2008) through which these imperatives can be woven into professional practice, offering a coherent pathway for systemic adoption. Finally, and most significantly, the theory proposes that when enabling conditions are present, acquisition of new competencies, supportive policy environments, and professional advocacy, the QS evolves into a future role: no longer a mere custodian of costs, but a sustainability strategist embedded at the heart of climate action.

Boundaries and Conditions of the Theory

According to Dubin (1969), a robust theory must make explicit the boundaries within which it holds true. The Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory is thus situated within a clearly defined set of conditions. Geographically, it is bounded to South Africa, a nation marked by acute socio-economic inequalities, a carbon-intensive economy, and profound vulnerability to climate impacts. Professionally, it speaks most directly to the field of Quantity Surveying, though its principles carry potential relevance for other built environment disciplines that similarly mediate cost, value, and sustainability. Temporally, it is oriented toward the contemporary and near-future horizon of the 2020s and 2030s, a period in which climate imperatives are projected to intensify and global sustainability frameworks, most notably the Sustainable Development Goals and the Paris Agreement converge to shape the trajectory of built environment transformation.

The Three Theoretical System States of Sustainable Development in the Built Environment

Dubin (1969) also emphasises that theories must account for system dynamics, recognising that professional practice evolves not in static form but through identifiable states of change. Within SCABE Theory, three such states are discerned. The first is a 'cost-centric equilibrium', in which the traditional role of the Quantity Surveyor predominates and barriers to transformation, skills deficits, cost perceptions, and regulatory inertia overwhelm emerging drivers.

Figure 1 First State of Cost-centric Equilibrium

The second is a phase of ‘transitional disequilibrium’, where mounting sustainability and climate imperatives destabilise the established order, developing tensions and competing pressures that force the profession to confront its limitations.

Figure 2 Second State of Transitional Disequilibrium

Figure 3 Third State of Sustainability-centric Equilibrium

The third is a ‘sustainability-centric equilibrium’, envisioned as the normalised state in which the Future QS Role is embedded across policy, practice, and education, and the SCABE framework is fully operationalised as a guide to professional conduct.

Interpretation, Abduction and Contribution Statement

SCABE Theory thus serves two functions. Descriptively, it abductively explains the current disjuncture between QS practice and sustainability imperatives, framed through the knowing–doing gap. Normatively, it interpretively explores a roadmap for professional transformation, situating QSs as systemic enablers of resilience and sustainable value. By employing Dubin, (1969) framework for theory building, SCABE achieves theoretical coherence: its constructs, propositions, boundaries, and system states collectively articulate how and under what conditions QSs may evolve into agents of sustainability and climate action.

This contribution is significant. Without SCABE, the QS profession risks marginalisation, trapped within outdated cost-centric paradigms as sustainability leadership shifts to other built environment professionals. With SCABE, QSs can reassert relevance, bridging financial expertise with climate-responsive design, and positioning themselves as architects of sustainable transformation in South Africa and beyond.

Figure 4 Descriptive and Normative Theoretical Framework for Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment. SCABE Theory as an interpretive framework for the evolving role of the Quantity Surveyor, adapted using Dubin’s (1978) approach to theory building. The model illustrates the progression from traditional QS roles, through barriers and enablers, toward a sustainability-oriented professional identity integrated within climate action.

The diagram presents not a static snapshot but a dynamic narrative of professional evolution, tracing how the Quantity Surveyor (QS) moves from a cost-centric identity toward a sustainability-oriented role in response to the imperatives of climate and resilience. At its foundation, traditional competencies and drivers anchor the QS within the familiar contours of financial oversight and contractual precision. This “Traditional QS Role” has long provided stability to the profession, yet its very narrowness now reveals profound limitations in the face of the multidimensional challenges of the built environment. From this

baseline, the model charts a progression shaped by tension. Current competencies, sustained by traditional drivers, form the bedrock of professional practice, but the persistence of competency barriers, skills deficits, knowledge gaps, and ‘institutional inertia’, acts as a drag on transformation. These barriers mediate the profession’s capacity to respond, tempering its ability to act decisively upon the mounting demands of sustainability and climate imperatives. Yet the narrative is not one of constraint alone. The framework also reveals the catalytic role of future drivers: digitalisation, green finance, escalating energy costs, and regulatory momentum. These forces interact with sustainability imperatives to create new vectors of possibility, enabling the QS profession to pivot from its inherited role toward one that is both more expansive and more strategically consequential.

At the heart of the diagram lies this crucial transition, the shift to the QS Strategic Role, in which the professional remit expands beyond financial stewardship to encompass advisory functions rooted in sustainability literacy, lifecycle evaluation, and resilience planning. This transition is neither inevitable nor automatic; it demands the deliberate overcoming of barriers and the embedding of new forms of knowledge and practice. It is precisely at this juncture that the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory is situated, serving as both a conceptual framework and a practical guide to reconcile cost, value, and sustainability into an integrated professional ethos.

The trajectory culminates in the Future QS Role, envisioned as a sustainability strategist who fuses financial rigour with long-term environmental and social value creation. Here, the QS is no longer merely the custodian of costs but becomes a strategic architect of resilience, equity, and sustainable transformation within the built environment.

Discussion

In positioning the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory within the wider constellation of contemporary frameworks (none of which form a complete theory), it is necessary to recognise that recent years have produced several influential contributions to the discourse on sustainability transitions in the built environment. Each of these frameworks illuminates vital dimensions of transformation, yet each leaves important gaps that SCABE is uniquely positioned to address.

Winkelmann et al. (2022), for instance, have developed a conceptual framework that describes the notion of social tipping processes, showing how small perturbations may cascade into systemic transitions toward sustainability. While valuable for understanding macro-level dynamics, such accounts remain abstract when translated into professional practice. SCABE enriches this discourse by situating tipping logic within a specific domain, demonstrating how Qs, through their advisory roles on cost and value, may serve as critical agents in accelerating or retarding such tipping points. In a complementary vein, Ho et al. (2024) have synthesised the concepts of Green Building and Circular Building, presenting ecological performance and regenerative design as twin pillars of sustainable construction. Their framework provides a powerful technical vision, but it is primarily concerned with design and systems engineering. SCABE extends this by foregrounding the mediating role of Qs, who transform such ideals into project-level feasibility, procurement decisions, and lifecycle evaluations, thereby providing the essential “last mile” between conceptual building theory and practical adoption. The same integrative move can be seen when SCABE is set against the work of Tanguay & Amor (2024), who have sought to connect hazard-induced damage models with environmental performance metrics in order to advance resilient built environments. While rigorous, their approach privileges systems modelling and tends to overlook the human agents responsible for embedding resilience in contracts, valuations, and risk frameworks. Here again, SCABE offers an important complement: it situates resilience not only in models but in professional practice, ensuring that resilience frameworks are operationalised in projects rather than confined to technical abstraction. Similarly, Bullinger and Schiller (2025) have explored social innovation in the circular built environment, identifying the institutional, governance, and behavioural levers that underpin transformative practice. Yet their emphasis remains socio-institutional, underplaying the role of professional mediation. SCABE addresses this lacuna by positioning the QS as a pivotal actor in orchestrating such innovations, deploying financial modelling, contractual structures, and procurement strategies to give institutional form to circularity.

Taken together, these comparisons reveal the epistemological significance of SCABE Theory. Where other frameworks privilege systemic, technical, or institutional dimensions, SCABE provides a profession-specific interpretive theory that bridges macro imperatives with micro practice, global

agendas with project realities. By employing Dubin (1969) model of theory building, it articulates constructs, propositions, boundaries, and system states that transform the discourse from descriptive abstraction into a coherent mid-level theory of professional transformation. Its distinctive contribution lies in demonstrating that professions themselves, here, the Quantity Surveyor, are not passive recipients of sustainability imperatives, but reflexive agents Eisenhardt (1989) whose evolving competencies, decisions, and voices are central to achieving sustainable climate action in practice.

Conclusion

This study has critically examined the evolving role of the QS within South Africa's built environment, positioning sustainability and climate action not as optional considerations but as defining imperatives for the profession's future. A narrative literature review revealed five interlinked themes: the centrality of sustainability and climate imperatives, the limitations of the traditional QS role, the persistence of barriers to transformation, the emergence of new drivers and opportunities, and the competencies required for practice in a changing landscape. Considered together, these themes expose the persistent "knowing-doing gap" that separates policy ambition from professional reality, underscoring the need for a coherent framework to guide transformation. It is in response to this need that the Sustainable Climate Action in the Built Environment (SCABE) Theory is advanced. Drawing upon the Dubin (1969) model of theory building, SCABE identifies the constructs, propositions, and system states that chart the trajectory from a cost-centric identity to a sustainability-oriented role, positioning the QS not as a passive custodian of costs but as an active agent of climate-responsive value creation. The theory demonstrates how the profession's traditional influence, in cost advice, procurement, and lifecycle evaluation, can be leveraged to operationalise sustainability imperatives and embed climate action into mainstream practice.

The epistemological contribution of SCABE is twofold: descriptively, it illuminates the disjuncture between present practice and the demands of sustainability transitions; normatively, it articulates a pathway for the QS to evolve into a strategic enabler of resilience, circularity, and long-term value. In dialogue with recent theoretical developments, such as social tipping processes Winkelmann et al. (2022), green and circular building frameworks Ho et al. (2024), resilient built environment models Tanguay and Amor (2024), and social innovation approaches Bullinger and Schiller (2025), SCABE offers a profession-specific perspective that bridges the macro imperatives of sustainability with the micro practices of project delivery. The QS profession now stands at a critical juncture: to resist this evolution is to risk marginalisation as sustainability leadership shifts to other actors, but to embrace the SCABE framework is to claim a central role in shaping a just, resilient, and sustainable future. For academia, industry, policymakers, and professional bodies alike, this is more than a professional transformation; it is an ethical imperative that binds the built environment to the service of society and the planet.

Recommendations and Implications

The findings of this study make plain that the transition of the QS from a narrowly cost-centric figure to a sustainability-oriented professional identity cannot be achieved through individual upskilling alone. It requires systemic change across multiple domains of influence, education, professional practice, policy, and the leadership of professional bodies. Within the sphere of education and research, universities and training institutions must embed QS Sustainability Literacy (SL) (a phenomenon coined in this study), life cycle assessment (LCA), and circular economy (CE) principles at the very heart of the QS curriculum. Such programmes should not confine themselves to technical competence but must cultivate habits of critical reasoning, ethical discernment, and leadership capacity, preparing Qs to serve as advocates of sustainability in practice. Further empirical research, whether through surveys, case studies, or longitudinal analyses, is also essential, in order to test and refine the propositions of the SCABE framework and secure its relevance to evolving professional practice. Future studies should explore and explain using SCABE as its theoretical framework.

In the realm of professional practice, Qs must move decisively beyond conventional cost control and embrace tools that enable long-term value assessment, including whole life costing (WLC), BIM-enabled sustainability modelling, and climate risk frameworks. Professional firms should be encouraged to integrate sustainability into their procurement strategies and fee structures, rewarding practices that deliver resilience and environmental value alongside financial accountability. By presenting clear, evidence-based cost-benefit analyses of sustainable interventions, Qs can play a

vital role in dispelling the persistent perception that sustainability is synonymous with prohibitive upfront costs. The domain of policy and governance remains equally critical. Governments should strengthen regulatory frameworks, enforce compliance with green building codes, and create enabling conditions through coherent incentives, tax credits, and sustainability-linked financing. At the same time, it is imperative that policymakers acknowledge QSs as strategic stakeholders in climate policy discourse, ensuring that their expertise informs and shapes national sustainability agendas, as such a information campaign must be launched by the relevant stakeholders.

Finally, professional bodies and leadership such as the ASAQS and SACQSP must assume a decisive role in championing this transformation. They should set sustainability-oriented standards, updating the standard system of measurement to have a trade deictated to sustainability, include and develop financial formulae that express the returns surrounding sustainability emphasising Returns on Sustainable Investment (ROSI), expand opportunities for continuing professional development (CPD), and promote diversity and inclusion within the profession. By adopting a unified and vocal stance in public and policy arenas, these bodies can elevate QS expertise to its rightful place as a cornerstone of sustainable transformation.

Taken together, these recommendations underscore that QSs cannot remain confined within the traditional cost-management paradigm. If empowered by education, supported through enabling policy, and galvanised by professional leadership, they can become linchpins in South Africa's transition to sustainability. The adoption of the SCABE Theory therefore carries implications far beyond the profession itself: it speaks to the resilience, inclusivity, and long-term viability of the built environment as a whole.

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